

THE HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE "LADY LIKE" STYLE.

Umarova Shaxzoda Faxriddinovna

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, Tashkent
Xalqaro Parish Fashion Academy, 2-year Master's Degree

Abstract: This paper examines the history of the emergence and development of the "Lady Like" style as a key trend in women's fashion, based on ideas of elegance, sophistication, and emphasized femininity. The development of the style's aesthetic and design features is analyzed in the context of social and cultural changes of the 20th century, as well as the influence of fashion trends and leading designers on its development. Particular attention is paid to the evolution of the women's suit, particularly the jacket, as an important wardrobe element reflecting the transformation of ideas about femininity and the role of women in society.

Keywords: "Lady Like" style, women's fashion, elegance, femininity, fashion history, 20th century, women's suit, jacket, silhouette, fashion trends, clothing design, aesthetics.

The "Lady Like" style emerged as a fashion trend based on the ideals of elegance, sophistication, and emphasized femininity. Its development is closely linked to the evolution of women's clothing, particularly the jacket, which throughout the 20th century became a key wardrobe element reflecting social and aesthetic changes. We're sure everyone remembers the story of those years—the entire world was desperately trying to leave the horrors of World War II behind. The general mood of those times was reflected in everything—the visual arts, music, literature, and, of course, fashion. After the difficult 1940s, the "Thaw" arrived. Financial crisis gave way to economic growth, and people craved luxury. This was especially true for women—they craved beauty, sophistication, and refinement. The result was an incredibly feminine style of clothing, now known as "Lady Like."

The origins of the Lady Like style date back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries, when strict canons of appearance were established in women's fashion. Jackets of the time were distinguished by their complex cut, sharp shoulders, defined waists, and decorative trim. They served not only a practical but also a status function, shaping the image of a respectable and well-bred woman [1].

A significant stage in the development of the Lady Like style is associated with the mid-20th century, particularly the post-war period. In 1947, Christian Dior introduced the New Look silhouette, which had a decisive influence on the development of the feminine jacket. Fitted styles with soft shoulders, a defined waist, and a graceful fit became the foundation of the Lady Like aesthetic. During this period, the jacket acquired the importance of a central element of the outfit, emphasizing the figure and creating a harmonious, elegant look. In the 1950s, Lady-Like jackets were distinguished by their use of high-quality fabrics, precise construction, and decorative details such as buttons, collars, lapels, and peplums. These features cemented the jacket's status as a symbol of femininity and refined taste. The style was actively supported by the images of iconic women of the era, which contributed to its popularization.

Leading fashion houses and designers had a significant influence on the development of this style, especially Christian Dior, who introduced the famous "New Look" in the mid-20th century. This style brought back refined femininity, luxurious fabrics, and the hourglass silhouette, becoming the foundation for the further development of the "Lady-Like" aesthetic.

Dresses and skirts are most often used to create this style. They can be full or straight, made from a variety of fabrics. Pastel, dark, or light colors are preferred, preferably classic. Heels are preferred – stilettos, but other styles are also acceptable. To create this look, you can't do without

classic high-heeled shoes; this is the main highlight (Fig.

1).

Fig. 1. A new look for dresses and skirts.

Bags and jewelry can be of various sizes, both small and large. Clutches and square bags are welcome. It's important not to overdo it with accessories; they should complement your outfit and not overpower it with their brightness.

Accentuate your silhouette. The Lady Like style emphasizes the best features of a woman's figure; don't forget to complete the look with a beautiful belt.

Quality. Try to avoid cheap, low-quality items; it's better to buy less, but better. Moreover, shopping malls regularly have sales these days. Say no to bright patterns and embellishments. This style doesn't tolerate floral or animal prints, so you should opt for subdued colors [2].

Fitted jackets and vests are key elements of a Lady Like wardrobe, as they accentuate the natural curves of the figure and create a refined, elegant silhouette. Particular preference is given to styles with a clearly defined waistline, shallow necklines, and neat structural details. Such jackets create a harmonious look, visually "pulling" the figure together and lending it proportionality. Vests, in turn, can be worn as a stand-alone element or as part of a suit, adding formality and sophistication to the look.

Slim coats play an important role in creating an elegant look. They not only emphasize the femininity and neatness of the silhouette, but also visually elongate the figure, making it appear slimmer and more refined. This makes slim coats easily combined with both business and casual looks, while maintaining the understated luxury and elegance characteristic of the "Lady Like" style.

In the 1960s and 1970s, interest in the "Lady Like" style waned noticeably, due to dramatic changes in fashion and society. During this period, ideas of minimalism, practicality, and functionality in clothing were actively promoted, reflecting a desire for freedom, equality, and a rejection of excessive embellishment. Simpler silhouettes, comfortable materials, and versatile

shapes, suited to the dynamic lifestyle of the modern woman, came to the fore (Fig.

2).

Fig. 2. "Lady-like" in the 1960s and 1970s.

Despite this, the jacket did not lose its importance in the women's wardrobe; instead, it underwent a significant transformation. Its design became more simplified, its lines became strict and laconic, and decorative elements were minimal or completely absent. At the same time, the basic principles of the "Lady-like" style were preserved: neatness, structured form, and a pronounced aesthetic of the silhouette.

The "Lady-like" style experienced a revival in the late 20th and early 21st centuries, when leading designers returned to classic forms, refined silhouettes, and ideas of emphasized femininity. This process was a response to fatigue with the excessive minimalism and unisex aesthetics characteristic of previous decades, as well as to the desire to bring elegance, individuality, and romanticism back into fashion in women's styles [3]. Modern "Lady Like" jackets harmoniously combine traditional elements—a tailored cut, precise construction, a precise fit, and exquisite trim—with current fashion trends. These include comfort, functionality, versatility, and adaptability to everyday wear. As a result, these pieces can easily integrate into both business attire and more relaxed contemporary looks, while maintaining their elegant essence.

The "Lady Like" style is considered a promising and sought-after trend in women's jacket design. It allows for the creation of garments that combine elements of a classic suit with contemporary fashion. Designers actively experiment with shape, proportions, cut lines, fabric textures, and decorative elements, striving for a balance between tradition and innovation. Material selection: both classic suiting fabrics and modern stretch and blended materials are used, ensuring comfort and freedom of movement. Decorative solutions became more restrained, yet refined, with an emphasis on the quality of cut, precision lines, and trim details [4].

Its development is closely linked to the social and cultural changes of the 20th century, as well as the evolution of women's clothing, particularly the jacket, which became a key element of this trend. Throughout its development, the "Lady Like" style has repeatedly transformed under the influence of fashion trends. In the 1960s and 1970s, it gave way to more functional and minimalist designs. However, it did not disappear completely, surviving in simplified and more laconic forms. The revival of the style in the late 20th and early 21st centuries testifies to its enduring relevance and adaptability to modern fashion demands.

Thus, the "Lady Like" style continues to develop as a significant trend in women's clothing design, combining tradition and modern trends. It remains relevant thanks to its ability to emphasize femininity, create an aesthetically harmonious image, and meet the demands of contemporary fashion.

REFERENCES:

1. Koblyakova E. B. Fundamentals of designing rational sizes and shapes of clothing: monograph / E. B. Koblyakov. – M.: Light and food industry, 1984. – 208 p.
2. Chernova I.V. Theoretical foundations of integrated design of special heat-protective clothing: abstract of thesis. dis....cand. tech. Sci. ...cand. those. Sciences: 05.19.04. Shakhty, 2008. 394 p.
3. Poltarak D.I. and others. Methodology of the use of resources and education and teaching history. M. "Prosveshchenie" 1987.
4. Gaffarov Ya.Kh. Methods of using new pedagogical technologies in teaching special subjects. Educational methodical use. Tashkent-2008.

